

DEVELOPMENT OF WEB-APPLICATIONS FOR THE BUREAU FOR THE REPAIR OF APARTMENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7560912>

ABSTRACT: Relevance. In the matter of developing and creating Web pages on the Internet, a huge store of various methods, methods and technologies has been accumulated, many of which, unfortunately, are now conditionally applicable. The fact is that the hardware upgrade only progresses from year to year, and at an increasing rate (the empirical laws of the American computer technician Moore are still in force - the power of microprocessors doubles every year and a half and the cost of personal computer components decreases twice). Therefore, it seems relevant and practically important to consider the problem of designing a Web site in modern conditions using the full range of achievements accumulated in this area.

The aim of the work is to study the methodological and applied literature on the problems of designing and creating Web pages, summarizing the work experience of experienced developers, programmers and Web designers, as well as choosing the optimal strategy, methods and techniques for creating a personal or corporate Web site that embodies all Today advanced ideas and technologies.

KEYWORDS: determine the structure of Web-pages, choose a strategy for developing and creating a Web site, to study the software tools used for the development and creation of Web-sites.

Introduction

The Internet is developing quite rapidly. The number of publications devoted to the Web is growing rapidly, which foreshadows its wide distribution even in areas far from technology. The Internet is turning from a big toy for intellectuals into a full-fledged source of various useful information for any category of users.

In ten years, according to experts, about 50 percent of families (of course, so far only in developed countries) will use it daily. Television and radio receivers will not be replaced by computers, but will have a powerful processor, more memory, and in fact will themselves become computers in some respects.

It will be a time when any person who owns a computer can “download” articles, illustrations, video or audio information on any topic of interest with its help. He will be able to get this information when he wishes. After some time, artificial intelligence systems — parallel machine translation, as well as voice identification and voice recognition — will break the latest national and language barriers and make free transnational information exchange possible.

Relevance. In the matter of developing and creating Web pages on the Internet, a huge store of various methods, methods and technologies has been accumulated, many of which, unfortunately, are now conditionally applicable. The fact is that the hardware upgrade only progresses from year to year, and at an increasing rate (the empirical laws of the American computer technician Moore are still in force - the power of microprocessors doubles every year and a half and the cost of personal computer components decreases twice). Therefore, it seems relevant and practically important to consider the problem of designing a Web site in modern conditions using the full range of achievements accumulated in this area.

The aim of the work is to study the methodological and applied literature on the problems of designing and creating Web pages, summarizing the work experience of experienced developers, programmers and Web designers, as well as choosing the optimal strategy, methods and techniques for creating a personal or corporate Web site that embodies all Today advanced ideas and technologies.

In the process of achieving the goal set in the course work, it is necessary to solve a number of the following particular tasks:

- get acquainted with modern Internet technologies and, if possible, use them in their development;
- to study the software tools used for the development and creation of Web-sites;
- to identify and take into account the methods and ways of presenting on the web pages of various types of information that do not interfere with their accessibility;
- read the basic rules and recommendations for the development and creation of Web-sites and strictly follow them in their practice;
- determine the structure of Web-pages;
- choose a strategy for developing and creating a Web site.

Nowadays, when the Internet has become an integral part of our life, the ability to find any kind of online service has become an actuality.

Here you can also note the possibility of creating an apartment repair bureau. This site allows you to find any information on the service of apartment renovation. This site stores extensive information about any organization for this service or contact details of one representative of this organization. This site meets all the requirements for creating web technologies, as well as the issue of usability is taken into account so that the user can easily move on the links of this site.

In the following chapters will be a detailed description of the development technology of this site and its content, with a description of the screenshots of each link with code support.

The structure of this course work consists of two chapters, conclusion, used literature and applications where the code of the site that was developed is written.

The first chapter contains a purely analytical character. After the analysis to the development was made, we proceeded to the formulation of tasks that will be necessary to solve with the system development course. In the domain model, a description of the topic of the course work is given, namely, an apartment repair bureau. The primary list of requirements sets out all the criteria that must be taken into account when developing the site, as well as all the technologies that were used directly during the creation of the site.

The second chapter is of a practical nature in which an idea of the available site, an instruction to the user, a detailed plan for working with the site and screenshots, from which any person can get acquainted with the content and content of the site on this document, is already given.

In the conclusion provides a conclusion to this course work, describes the technologies used and the knowledge that was used in the development.

Object analysis and problem statement

1.1. Formulation of the problem

If you consider the site as an information system or software package (and the developers consider it so), then there have been and there are attempts to apply the appropriate terminology and design procedure based on GOST 1989. In my opinion, these attempts are not entirely successful - in 1989 WWW technology did not exist (it was invented in 1994), and in Uzbekitane there were neither marketing and management technologies, nor even a market (it appeared in a wild state in 1991, and market technologies even later). Therefore, it turns out to be stiff and one-sided in any case: writing documentation on state standards takes a lot of time, which does not work on project efficiency - we are

interested in the final business efficiency of the site, its consumer value, the design of which is not taken into account. In addition, they do not take into account the efficiency of interface design, ergonomics, etc., that is, the creation of user efficiency. Therefore, we will accept the term “problem statement” to describe the purpose and functionality of the site and we will continue to operate on them.

Task setting should be written as part of a systems approach. The classical formula of a systematic approach - goals, objectives, limitations and means. Goals, objectives and constraints dictate the reality of your business, and the means dictate technology development. Therefore, in the formulation of the problem, you work on what is included in the first three points: goals, objectives and limitations (plus conditions - information about the enterprise and the external environment in which it exists). And the developer is engaged in the fourth item - means of implementing the task within the specified limits. And everything turns out harmoniously and expediently.

Task setting is a very important stage in the work on the site. If the tasks are formulated correctly and clearly, even the unsuccessfully selected developer will cope with the project. And the main mistake that corporations make when creating a website is the underestimation of the added value that is laid at this stage.

As for the site itself, it should attract the user with its extensive content, whereby people will want to purchase repair services. The analysis showed that in the age of development and implementation of information technologies, services that can provide repair bureau to the next level, that is, you can now order services online without leaving home. You can get acquainted with the service directly through the site and order it too, for which it serves. The site will have extensive content that will give an idea about the services. The user can view the news regarding repair services, innovations in interior design, contact details and details of the bureau itself. I would also like to note that it will be possible to view and add comments to the service or the content in general. To order the service there is a separate form that the user must fill out.

1.2 Domain Model

The subject area of this course work is the creation of a web application for an apartment repair bureau. This site is like a business card for the repair organization. Each user or customer of the service has the opportunity to find the service and information that interests him.

In the analysis stage, all the questions that are necessary when developing our website were taken into account. Here is a screenshot of the approximate type of site and structure.

Fig. 1 Type of web application.

1.3 Primary requirements list

To the requirement of creating a site, you can add that this site must meet the criteria of usability. Here I tried to describe the most necessary requirements for creating a site.

Content, or filling the site with useful information. The site should attract visitors with quality articles, original photos and images. Full content is formed on its own, or through the involvement of professional professional copywriters and photographers.

2. Structure, that is, convenient placement of information on the site. The site should be organized so that a casual visitor can easily find information on the topic of interest on the tabs system. When creating a site, remember that a potential user is not ready for a long time to understand the complex system of transitions from page to page. The user prefers simple and clear solutions.

3. Design, or design. The style of the site is important for the formation of a positive impression of it. The design is welcomed bright personality that can inspire confidence in the content of the site. It is important that in the pursuit of the unique appearance of the site, its creator does not forget about the interests of visitors, and did not scare them too original design.

4. Update content. The site lives until new articles appear on it, funny pictures, great photos and video reports about events. Without the latest information, the site is doomed to oblivion and death.

5. Address, or posting on the Internet. To make the site credible, you should take care of its laconic name and placement on a paid hosting. Serious companies never use the services of "free sites", it adversely affects their image.

6. Site loading speed. The user will not wait for the download for more than four or five seconds. Therefore, when creating a website, record the download period using a stopwatch.

7. Sophisticated communication system with the visitor. Contacts to contact the site administration should be easily detectable. Provide several options: contact via email, by phone number, via online consultant. Quality feedback helps to create a circle of regular visitors to the site.

8. Indexing the site, its promotion. The main algorithm for finding information on the web is through search engines and key queries. Therefore, the site content must contain keywords and whole phrases with which search engines will redirect users to a specific site. Help users easily find your site.

9. Advertising. A site without ads looks suspicious. A site with an excess of advertising, with obsessive banners and huge pop-up windows makes you want to immediately leave it forever. Caring for additional income through advertising should not harm the very existence of the site.

10. Integration with social networks. Almost all the time on the Internet, users spend in their favorite social networks. Use any means of placing links to your site in networks, and lure visitors to yourself!

In the online store and the client and the owner feel as comfortable as possible. Here you can find as long as you like, do not rush to buy, book goods, choose the method of payment and delivery. If the owner of the online store is right in promoting it, it doesn't allow the trade to drift, it can bode well, especially if the store's website has a beautiful design, a good product catalog, flexible prices, discounts for regular customers and other attractive chips that attract customers .

Programming tools.

HTML is the standardized markup language for documents on the World Wide Web. Most web pages contain HTML (or XHTML) markup. HTML is interpreted by browsers; formatted text resulting from interpretation is displayed on the monitor of a computer or mobile device.

The HTML language up to version 5 was defined as an SGML application (standard generalized markup language according to ISO8879). HTML5 specifications are formulated in terms of DOM (Document Object Model).

XHTML is a more rigorous version of HTML, it follows XML syntax and is an XML application in the hypertext markup area.

On the World Wide Web, HTML pages are usually transmitted to browsers from the server using HTTP or HTTPS protocols, in plain text or using encryption.

Text documents containing HTML markup (such documents traditionally have the .html or .htm extension) are processed by special applications that display the document in its formatted form. Such applications, called “browsers” or “Internet browsers,” usually provide the user with a convenient interface for requesting web pages, viewing them (and outputting to other external devices) and, if necessary, sending user-entered data to the server. The most popular browsers today are Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Opera, Internet Explorer and Safari.

HTML - tagged markup language documents. Any HTML document is a set of elements, with the beginning and end of each element indicated by special marks - tags. Items may be empty, that is, they do not contain any text or other data (for example, the line wrapping tag
). In this case, the closing tag is usually not specified. In addition, elements can have attributes that define some of their properties (for example, the font size for the tag). Attributes are specified in the opening tag.

CSS (/ siksēs / English. Cascading Style Sheets - cascading style sheets) is a formal language for describing the appearance of a document written using a markup language.

It is mainly used as a means of describing, shaping the appearance of web pages written using HTML and XHTML markup languages, but can also be applied to any XML documents, for example, SVG or XUL.

CSS is usually used by the creators and developers of web pages to specify colors, fonts, the location of individual blocks and other aspects of the appearance of these web pages. The main purpose of developing CSS was to separate the description of the logical structure of a web page (which is produced using HTML or other markup languages) from the description of the appearance of this web page (which is now produced using the formal CSS language). This separation can increase the availability of a document, provide greater flexibility and control over its presentation, as well as reduce complexity and repeatability in structured content. In addition, CSS allows you to present the same document in different styles or output methods, such as screen

presentation, print presentation, voice reading (with a special voice browser or screen reader), or when outputted by devices using Braille.

CSS rules are written in the formal CSS language and are located in style sheets, that is, style sheets contain CSS rules. These style sheets can be located both in the web document itself, the appearance of which they describe, and in separate files that have a CSS format. (Essentially, the CSS format is a plain text file. The .css file contains nothing but a list of CSS rules and comments for them.)

PHP (/pi:.ertf.pi:/ English PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor - “PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor”; originally Personal Home Page Tools - “Tools for creating personal web pages”) is a general-purpose scripting language used extensively for web application development. Currently supported by the overwhelming majority of hosting providers and is one of the leaders among the languages used to create dynamic websites.

The language and its interpreter (Zend Engine) are developed by a group of enthusiasts in an open source project. The project is distributed under its own license, incompatible with the GNU GPL.

In the field of web programming, in particular, server-side, PHP is one of the popular scripting languages (along with JSP, Perl, Python, and the languages used in ASP.NET).

Popularity in the field of building websites is determined by the presence of a large set of built-in tools for developing web applications. The main ones are:

- automatic extraction of POST and GET parameters, as well as environment variables of the web server into predefined arrays;
- interaction with a large number of different database management systems (MySQL, MySQL, SQLite, PostgreSQL, Oracle (OCI8), Oracle, Microsoft SQL Server, Sybase, ODBC, mSQL, IBM DB2, Cloudscape and Apache Derby, Informix, Ovrimos SQL, Lotus Notes, DB ++, DBM, dBase, DBX, FrontBase, FilePro, Ingres II, SESAM, Firebird / InterBase, Paradox File Access, MaxDB, PDO Interface);
- automated sending of HTTP headers;
- work with HTTP authorization;
- work with cookies and sessions;
- work with local and remote files, sockets;
- processing files uploaded to the server;
- work with XForms.

Currently, PHP is used by hundreds of thousands of developers. According to the rating of TIOBE corporation, based on data from search engines, in May

2016, PHP was in 6th place among programming languages. The largest sites using PHP include Facebook, Wikipedia, and others.

Included in LAMP - a common set of software for creating and hosting websites (Linux, Apache, MySQL, PHP).

Although PHP is not very common in this area, it can also be used to create GUI applications.

To create cross-platform applications, use the PHP-GTK and PHP-Qt packages, which are wrappers for the corresponding popular widget libraries. There is also a development environment for cross-platform applications Devel Next.

To create graphical applications for Windows, there are free WinBinder packages (written in C, in fact, a wrapper for WinAPI), PQBuilder (written in PHP using the PHPQt5 library), and also the predecessor of Devel Next, the rapid development environment of Devel Studio.

In addition, there is a PHP implementation for .NET / Mono - Phalanger and for JVM - JPHP, the result of compiling PHP code into Phalanger can be any .NET application, while JPHP supports the Swing extension, almost completely ported from Java.

PHP is a programming language with dynamic typing, which does not require a type indication when declaring variables, nor is the declaration of variables itself. Conversions between scalar types are often implicitly implemented without additional efforts (however, PHP provides ample opportunities for explicit type conversion).

Scalar data types include:

- integer type (integer)
- floating point number (float, double)
- boolean type
- string type

Non-scalar types include:

- array (array)
- object
- external resource
- null

Pseudo-types include:

- mixed any type
- number number (integer or float)
- callback (string or anonymous function)

- void missing parameters

The range of integers (integer) in PHP depends on the platform (usually, this is the range of 32-bit signed integers, that is, from -2,147,483,648 to 2,147,483,647). Numbers can be set in decimal, octal and hexadecimal number systems. The range of real numbers (double) also depends on the platform (for a 32-bit architecture, the range allows operating numbers from $\pm 1.7 \times 10^{-308}$ to $\pm 1.7 \times 10^{+308}$).

PHP provides developers with a boolean type that can take only two values: TRUE (true) and FALSE (false). When converting to a logical type, the number 0, the empty string, zero in the string "0", NULL and the empty array are considered equal to FALSE. All other values are automatically converted to TRUE.

The special type null is intended for variables without a specific value. The only value of this type is the constant NULL. The null type is accepted by uninitialized variables, variables initialized by a constant NULL, as well as variables deleted using the unset () construct.

Links to external resources are of type "resource" (resource). Variables of this type, as a rule, are a descriptor that allows you to manage external objects, such as files, dynamic images, resulting database tables, etc.

Arrays (array) support numeric and string keys and are heterogeneous. Arrays can contain values of any type, including other arrays. The order of the elements and their keys is preserved. It is not entirely correct to call php arrays as arrays; in fact, this is most likely an ordered hash. Perhaps unexpected behavior when using a for loop with a counter instead of foreach. So, for example, when sorting an array with numerical indexes by functions from the standard library, the keys are also sorted.

2. Site design and user instructions

2.1. Project plan

Sell services through the Internet, has long become a habit for many. It is very popular and very convenient, because it allows you to save money, without leaving home, to do business, without paying taxes, rent and so on. To sell something through the site is a good idea, because it involves a minimum of investment and a maximum return that every commercial enterprise pursues. Selling sites can represent the interests of a small store or a huge production, orient to retail or wholesale customers, but the fact that the site helps to make sales and brings profit to its owners is tested by experience.

Sites created for the sale of services are significantly different from other sites, information resources, forums or presentation projects. Today, many private entrepreneurs, instead of opening stores on the ground, hiring working staff, paying crazy money for renting premises, simply create online stores, and this is really profitable, it works, it makes profit, and it helps to develop its business very successfully.

Analyzing, we decided that navigation will have 6 sections:

- 1) About us
- 2) Apartments
- 3) Reviews
- 4) FAQ (questions and answers)
- 5) Blog
- 6) Contacts

Scheme 1. Structure and site map

If you decide to create a website selling something, then the most important thing is to be guided by its specificity, by those goods and services that you plan to implement on this website.

You must provide a description of your store, organization, tell about the goods or services sold, focus on why the client should make a purchase, than your products and services are better than others.

The selling sites should also indicate the cost of goods and services, so that the client does not spend his and your time on finding out the rates, choose the most optimal payment methods and delivery of purchased goods, and in this matter you need to focus not only on what and how you will be comfortable, and first of all, convenient options for your customers, so there should be several and most common ones.

It is best to attach illustrations to the goods, high resolution, so that the buyer can see for what he will pay the money. If you can take photos of the product that you have, it will increase the likelihood of its sale, and after the site

starts working and you have your first customers, be sure to create a section where they can post their reviews, this will increase the level of trust you as a seller and customers will be more likely to contact your service.

2.2 Key features and requirements

Sites focused on the sale of goods or services may be different, basically, the most common are three such types:

1. - online store;
2. - online store showcase;
3. - online product catalog.
4. Site business card services
5. Site selling the service with the possibility of review and order.

Based on the foregoing, our site will be as the site is suitable for the 5th category. Next we will describe and show the type of site being developed.

2.3 Examples from the creation of the site

First of all, create a template for our site in html format.

Below in the picture, opening the main page file in the browser, we will see the site view, as you can see in the status bar there are special tools for working and editing

Fig. 2 Example of the main page of the site

Below is the content that describes the approximate view of the apartment, which will be after repair. The user can find this information by going to the Apartments tab.

Fig. 3 Example of a block of apartment page


```
1 <!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD HTML 4.01 Transitional//EN" "http://www.w3.org/TR/html4/loose.dtd">
2 <html>
3 <head>
4 <meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8">
5 <title>Форма</title>
6 </head>
7 <body>
8 <form action="formdata.php" method="POST" name="form">
9 <fieldset>
10 <legend>Ввод личных данных</legend>
11 <strong><label>Введите Ваше имя (макс. 10 символов):</label><input type="text" name="name" hspace="10" size="30" maxlength="10"/></strong></p>
12 <strong><label>Введите Ваш пароль (макс. 10 символов):</label><input type="password" name="password" hspace="10" size="30" maxlength="10"/></strong></p>
13 </fieldset>
14 <fieldset>
15 <legend>Вопросы</legend>
16 <p>Вы хотите ли за экономить время?</p>
17 <label> Да</label><input type="radio" name="time" value="yes" checked=""/><label> Нет</label><input type="radio" name="time" value="no"/></p>
18 <p>Какие инструменты для экономии времени вы любите пользоваться?</p>
19 <p>
20 <label><input type="checkbox" name="ez">Экраны</label>
21 <label><input type="checkbox" name="T">Телепорт</label>
22 <label><input type="checkbox" name="as">Супер скорость</label>
23 </p>
24 <p><label for="hours">Сколько часов в день вы спите?</label></p>
25 <p>
26 <select name="sleep" id="hours">
27 <option value="5">5</option>
28 <option value="6">6</option>
29 <option value="7">7</option>
30 <option selected="" value="8">8</option>
31 <option value="9">9+ (больше 9ми часов)</option>
32 </select>
33 </p>
34 </form>
```

Fig. 4 Site homepage code

Next we have to put our template on our server so that we can dynamically manage our site. To do this, create our website header.

header.php:

Имя	↑ Тип	Размер	Дата
..		<Папка>	23.09.2017 08:36
description	php	129	22.09.2017 14:46
footer	php	15 198	02.03.2018 21:00
header	php	17 795	03.03.2018 10:43

Fig. 5 Example of the server part


```

1 <!DOCTYPE html>
2 <html lang="ru">
3 <head>
4 <meta charset="utf-8">
5 <meta http-equiv="X-UA-Compatible" content="IE=edge">
6 <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
7 <!-- The above 3 meta tags *must* come first in the head; any other head content must come *after* these tags -->
8 <title>Fast Service</title>
9 <!-- Bootstrap -->
10 <link href="assets/css/bootstrap.min.css" rel="stylesheet">
11 <link href="assets/css/style.css" rel="stylesheet">
12 <link rel="stylesheet" href="assets/css/font-awesome.min.css">
13 <!-- HTML5 shim and Respond.js for IE support of HTML5 elements and media queries -->
14 <!-- WARNING: Respond.js doesn't work if you view the page via file:// -->
15 <!--[if lt IE 9]>
16 <script src="https://oss.maxcdn.com/html5shiv/3.7.3/html5shiv.min.js"></script>
17 <script src="https://oss.maxcdn.com/respond/1.4.2/respond.min.js"></script>
18 <![endif]-->
19 </head>
20 <body>
21 <div class="container-fluid top-header">
22 <div class="row">
23 <div class="container">
24 <div>
25 <div class="col-lg-2 col-md-2 col-sm-3 col-xs-6">
26 <div class="row">
27 <li class="fa fa-phone" aria-hidden="true"></li><span class="contacts-top-header">+998 71 555-55-55</span>
28 </div>
29 </div>
30 <div class="col-lg-2 col-md-3 col-sm-2 col-xs-6">
31 <div class="row">
32 <p class="email">
33 <li class="fa fa-envelope" aria-hidden="true"></li><span class="contacts-top-header">mail@mail.com</span>

```

Fig. 6 Code header.php site pages

First of all we create information blocks for our site:

Information blocks are those categories, content, tabs that the user can navigate inside the site by clicking on the links. This site manager is the main part of the job for the administrator, from where he creates the content or

structure of the site.

Fig. 7 Creating an information block directory

Thus we create all our blocks that are automatically connected to the database.

This system automatically adds all the information to the database, from where all the content on the site appears.

Fig. 8 Created information blocks of elements

Go to the public part of the site add the content there:

This editor is for adding content, and in this case we are adding an apartment and detailed information so that the user can find out everything that interests him.

Fig. 9 Add content to the site

Next, we will continue until we finish editing the site content.

To add elements to our blocks, open them and insert the necessary image and text into them.

Fig. 10. item window

Fig. 11 Adding an item

After we have completed all the processes of adding content, the system automatically displays it on our website, as we see it.

Figure 12.

On the news page, as I mentioned earlier, there is information about the latest innovations in the field of repair, construction, and so on.

Figure 13.

The “About Us” page provides a brief and accurate description of the bureau, information about the services they provide.

Figure 14

In the Orders tab, the user will be able to find our details and contact us. Here detailed information about our address, contact details and e-mail. I would also like to draw attention to the fact that here the user will be able to order the service, leave their details and contact information to call him back.

Figure 15.

After that, in our database there is news that we received a request from the client. The database shows all the information regarding the client, which he filled out in the form.

Figure 16.

We also added a feedback page where our customers can leave their comments. Here, as well as the user, the bureau will be able to conduct an analysis, which will be able to improve and take into account user preferences.

Figure 17.

Conclusion

In conclusion, I would like to note that this site took into account all the requirements for the development and all knowledge gained during the training of this course was used. As for my subject area, namely the apartment repair bureau, I hope that this site meets all the criteria and design methods. I would also like to note that the site as a system is ready for operation and work in the information technology market, as part of a business of any company.

In any case, if you plan to do a selling business, create your own website for sales. The cost of creating it, even in the worst case, will definitely justify itself; pages.

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